

Biotreatment of diesel and evaluation of its physico-chemical properties

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Manuscript received 19 August 2011, accepted 23 September 2011

Abstract : Microbial treatment of diesel was carried out with the strain *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* OCD₁ in liquid Bushnell-Haas broth to study the changes in physico-chemical properties of treated diesel. The optimum culture conditions for this strain were obtained as temperature 30 °C, shaker speed 125 r.p.m and pH 6 in liquid Bushnell-Haas broth with 2% diesel as a substrate. The evaluation of physico-chemical properties reveals that the percentage of alkanes are reduced in the treated diesel as aniline point, diesel index, cetane number, pour point values were decreased for treated diesel compared to untreated diesel. This strain therefore can be used for the quality improvement of petroleum products with respect to pour point or for the purpose of dewaxing of lubricating oil base stock (LOBS).

Keywords : Biotreatment, diesel, physico-chemical properties, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

Introduction

Diesel is a complex mixture of hydrocarbons consisting mainly of three major groups; straight/branched chain alkanes, cycloalkanes/naphthenes and aromatics as well as NSO compounds and metals obtained as the middle-distillate of crude petroleum during atmospheric distillation. Diesel is used very frequently in our modern life as a fuel. The presence of aromatics/polyaromatics, NSO compounds i.e. nitrogen, sulfur, oxygen and metals in the diesel leads to various problems of which the environmental pollution is of most serious concern. This contamination are hazardous to the health of plants and are also carcinogenic, mutagenic and potent immuno-toxicants, posing a serious threat to human and animal health¹⁻⁵. Again, the undesirable component of diesel can create problem on its performance like high carbon residue, poor ignition quality, engine knocking, filter clogging etc. and simultaneously produce environmental pollutants. The recent advances in microbial technology for quality improvement of petroleum products with respect to cetane no., diesel index, octane no., pour point, viscosity etc. is being very interesting and attractive field of work. The biological technical service group of Chevron Phillips Chemical Company LP examined quality improvement of paraffinic and non-paraffinic oil with respect to viscosity, pour point etc. by the action of microbes⁶. The lit-

erature study supports that not much work has been done in the field of improvement of oil quality by microbial treatment.

Therefore, this work aims to study the microbial treatment of diesel with an air isolate *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* OCD₁ and to assess the physico-chemical characteristics of the treated diesel in relation to original one in order to produce environment friendly products of good quality.

Results and discussion

Optimization of culture conditions :

On the basis of optical density (O.D.) of the growth culture, the optimum temperature was selected as 30 °C. The strain OCD₁ favours relatively slow shaking. Increasing shaker speed to more than 125 r.p.m led to decreased growth of the strain thus 125 r.p.m was taken as optimum. Similarly, pH was chosen as 6.0 depending on growth of culture broth. The results are shown in following figures (Figs. 1, 2 and 3).

Treatment of diesel :

During the treatment of different percentage of diesel with *P. aeruginosa* OCD₁ heavy growth was observed after four days incubation in all the flasks containing 2, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25% of diesel. At the same time it was found that some amount of diesel was left as unconverted

Fig. 1. Optimization of temperature.

Fig. 2. Optimization of shaker speed.

Fig. 3. Optimization of pH of culture media.

oil in the flasks containing higher percentage of diesel. Similar type of study was carried out by Rahaman *et al.* for biodegradation of crude oil by selected isolates with various concentration of crude oil (1–10%)⁷. It is interesting to note that the organism OCD₁ showed significant growth with higher percentage of diesel also even with 90% (v/v) of oil content i.e. the higher percentage of diesel does not inhibit the growth of organism.

Successive treatment of diesel and changes in physico-chemical properties of diesel :

After treating the diesel in three successions, the properties of the treated oil were measured to observe the improvement of oil quality by microbial treatment. From the comparative study of physico-chemical properties of treated and untreated diesel (Table 1), it is observed that the alkanes get depleted in the treated diesel on treatment with *P. aeruginosa* OCD₁ thus aniline point, diesel index, cetane no., cetane index, pour point values decreased whereas specific gravity, viscosity values were increased. This results support that, the strain OCD₁ is a paraffin degrader hence pour point reduction can be achieved with this microorganism in order to improve the flow property and filter clogging of diesel. Low pour point and CFPP (Cold Filter Plugging Point) of diesel is desirable for its better engine performance.

Table 1. Comparative study of physico-chemical properties of treated (after 3rd treatment) diesel and untreated diesel

Properties	Untreated diesel	Treated diesel
Sp. gravity at 15.5 °C/15.5 °C	0.8229	0.8329
Kinematic viscosity at 38 °C, cSt	2.085	2.463
Aniline point (°C)	70	68
Diesel Index	63.92	59.27
Cetane no.	56.02	52.67
Cetane Index	57.48	54.85
Pour point (°C)	-13.5	-16.2

Therefore, the strain *P. aeruginosa* OCD₁ with its paraffin degrading ability can successfully be utilized for quality improvement of the petroleum products with respect to pour point, or for the purpose of dewaxing of LOBS.

Materials and methods :

Microorganism :

The strain *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* OCD₁⁸ was isolated from air in the laboratory by the present authors.

Diesel :

High Speed Diesel (HSD) was procured from the retail Market.

Media, chemicals and solvents :

Bushnell-Haas (BH) broth, peptone, beef extract powder, Agar agar type I – Hi-Media; NaCl, chloroform,

ethanol, methanol – Merck; acetone, dichloromethane – SRL.

Other chemicals and solvents of AR grade are procured from local supplier.

Optimization of culture conditions for better degradation of diesel :

The physical parameters like temperature, agitation and pH have great influence on growth of organisms and also on the rate of degradation of diesel. All these optimization studies were performed using liquid BH media with 2% diesel as the sole C-source for the microorganisms. Optical density of the culture broth was measured at 600 nm with variation of different parameters under study, keeping other variables constant at a time.

Treatment of diesel :

Shake flasks studies were performed for treatment of diesel. Fresh overnight culture was taken to inoculate the sterile BH media containing different percentage of diesel ranging from 2–25% (v/v). The flasks were kept under shaking condition in a shaker incubator (ORBITEK L J E, Scigenics Biotech (Pvt.) Ltd., India) at optimum culture conditions for four days. The experiment was also repeated with higher percentage (upto 90 vol%) of diesel.

Successive treatment of diesel and changes in physico-chemical properties :

It was found that after the treatment of higher percentages of diesel some amount of diesel was left over. Hence we were interested to treat that left over diesel with a fresh lot of culture again. The diesel (10 vol%) was treated three times successively in the same procedure mentioned above. The treated oil of the first step was treated again with fresh culture and so on. Every time similar huge growth was observed in case of treated oil. Finally after third treatment, oil was separated and tested for the changes in corresponding physico-chemical properties. A comparative study of the properties was then performed using the untreated diesel and treated diesel after third treat-

ment. Standard ASTM methods were used for studying the physico-chemical properties of the untreated and the treated diesel, e.g. Aniline Point : ASTM D 611⁹; Pour Point : ASTM D 97¹⁰; Kinematic Viscosity : ASTM D 445¹¹.

Following standard correlations were also used for further assessment¹² :

$$^{\circ}\text{API} = (141.5/\text{sp. gr. (15.5 }^{\circ}\text{C}/15.5 }^{\circ}\text{C})) - 131.5$$

$$\text{Diesel Index (D.I)} = \text{Aniline Point (}^{\circ}\text{F)} \times ^{\circ}\text{API}/100$$

$$\text{Cetane No.} = (0.72 \times \text{Diesel Index}) + 10$$

$$\text{Cetane Index} = (0.566 \times \text{Diesel Index}) + 21.3$$

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to University Grants Commission (UGC), New Delhi for the financial support.

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